

INVESTIGATION INTO 3D PRINTING OF CFRP USING COVERING COMPOSITE YARN

TAKATO YOSHIKAWA¹, TAKASHI MATSUOKA², TOMOKO HIRAYAMA³,
HIDETOSHI SAKAMOTO⁴

¹⁻⁴Dep. Of Mechanical Engineering, Doshisha University,
Tataramiyakodani 1-3, Kyotanabe, Kyoto, 610-0321 Japan
¹email:ctwc0606@mail4.doshisha.ac.jp

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, weight reduction of parts has been required for the purpose of improving fuel economy in the automobile industry etc. CFRP attracts attention because of its high specific strength. As a molding of CFRP using continuous carbon fiber, there is a problem that it is difficult to produce a wide variety of products in small quantity because the mold is used in heat press forming which is a conventional molding method.

On the other hand, molding with a 3D printer that allows free manufacturing without a mold has attracted attention. However, as the main feed material is a resin material, there is a problem in terms of strength.

Therefore, researches are under way to form CFRP with a 3D printer. However, there are problems such as molding failure due to insufficient resin around the fiber bundle when the fiber volume content rate is improved. The characteristic of the covering composite yarn is that the impregnation of the resin into the nozzle can be changed depending on the molding conditions, and the necessary amount of resin can be uniformly supplied around the carbon fiber.

As a result of studies on resin impregnation inside the nozzle, the porosity increased with the increase of the nozzle diameter, which was almost the same as the theoretical value. It was possible to control the porosity inside the nozzle depending on the nozzle diameter.

In the bending test of the laminated material, the smaller the nozzle diameter, the smaller the porosity and the strength improved. Increasing the speed during the production of the laminate material shortened the forming time. However, the bending strength decreased.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, weight reduction of parts has been required in the aircraft and automobile industries for the purpose of improving fuel consumption from the viewpoint of increasing interest in environmental problems and energy saving [1]. Therefore, although relatively lightweight metals are used, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has attracted attention as an alternative material for further weight reduction. Features of CFRP include higher specific strength and superior dimensional stability than metals, and its use in various fields such as sports products and medical devices has also been tried. Thermosetting resin has been used for conventional CFRP, but those using thermoplastic resin as the base material are called Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic (CFRTP), and post-processing is easy compared to thermosetting CFRP and production is possible. It has attracted attention because of its superiority [2]. In addition, since the strength and the rigidity are improved as the fiber length of the reinforcing fiber used is longer, higher strength can be expected by using continuous fibers instead of short fibers and long fibers. The prepreg method [2] and the film stacking method [3] are mentioned as a forming method of CFRP using continuous carbon fiber. In these molding methods, there are problems such as poor stretch ability and difficulty in forming complex shapes due to the use of prepreg sheets, and that molding of the mold is costly and time-consuming [3].

On the other hand, in recent years, molding using a 3D printer has attracted attention as a new manufacturing method. The characteristic of molding is that preparation of a prototype can be performed in a short time, a mold is unnecessary and free design is possible, and shape change is possible only by changing a program [4]. However, resin materials such as ABS and PLA are the

mainstream as a supply material used for 3D printers, and there are problems in terms of strength.

Therefore, research on forming CFRP which is a high strength supply material by 3D printer is advanced, and application to products requiring strength such as power transmission parts is expected. As a research example, there is a method that uses CFRP containing short fibers as a supply material, but the strength is not improved so much because the short fibers are discontinuous [5]. In addition, in the method of supplying fiber and resin from different directions and impregnating inside the nozzle, it is necessary to impregnate inside the nozzle, the fiber volume content cannot be improved, and the strength is not improved so much [6]. In the method of using filaments in which resin is impregnated with continuous carbon fibers in advance, if the fiber volume content is improved, a failure occurs such that the resin in the vicinity of the fiber bundle is insufficient and the layers do not adhere. Filament is used and strength does not reach to general CFRP [7].

Therefore, in this study, we used a covering composite yarn in which resin is coated around the carbon fiber as a supply material. The characteristic of the covering composite yarn is that the carbon fiber is covered with the resin yarn, so that it can be prevented from being broken and the carbon fiber bundle is not dispersed at the time of removing the convergence agent so that the work becomes easy. In addition, since resin is uniformly present, resin can be supplied uniformly in the fiber bundle, and resin cannot be impregnated in the fiber bundle, so that resin impregnation inside the nozzle can be controlled by molding conditions.

In this study, we aimed to understand the influence of molding conditions on the impregnation state and mechanical properties of resin in 3D printed products using covering composite yarn. Based on the results of last year, laminate materials were molded under various molding conditions in order to understand the impregnation properties and mechanical properties of 3D printed products.

2 MATERIAL AND MATERIAL PREPARATION METHOD

2.1 SAMPLE PREPARATION

For the covering composite yarn, carbon fiber(T300B-3000-50B) is used as the reinforcing material and nylon yarn PA6 resin (70d 2-24f-VF555-BC) is used as the base material. Three nozzles with diameters of 0.64 mm, 0.71 mm, and 0.80 mm were prepared for 3D printers. In this study, CFRP forming was carried out by independently making and changing nozzles suitable for CFRP forming using covering composite yarn.

2.2 STRUCTURE AND FEATURES OF COVERING COMPOSITE YARN

As a supply material for 3D printer in this research, we used a covering composite yarn in which resin yarn was covered on a knit around a carbon fiber using a knitting machine. The appearance of the knitting machine is shown in Fig. 2.1 An enlarged view of the covering composite yarn is shown in Fig. 2.2 The characteristic of the covering composite yarn is that the carbon fiber is covered with the resin yarn so that the carbon fiber is prevented from being broken, and the carbon fiber bundle is covered with the resin yarn when removing the carbon fiber convergence agent Since the fiber bundle and the resin are in close contact with each other, the impregnation can be improved because the fiber bundle and the resin are in close contact with each other, and the fiber and the resin are separately present. It is possible to change the state of impregnation.

Fig.2.1: Knitting machine

Fig.2.2: Covering composite yarn

2.3 MATERIAL PREPARATION METHOD

After the covering composite yarn was made, it was dipped and cleaned in acetone for 60 minutes to remove the sizing agent attached to the carbon fiber. After washing, the resin contained moisture in the air and acetone, which caused voids, and was left for 12 hours in a furnace at 60 ° C. for drying, and used as a supply material for the 3D printer.

The heater temperature of the 3D printer was 240 ° C in this study. This is because the melting point of the used resin is 225 ° C, and the resin is reliably melted while considering the control characteristics of the heater temperature. Also, to make it easy to remove the molded product, apply a polyimide tape to the table and prepare a sample on it. First, the nozzle is moved vertically to the table to make a sample, and the impregnation state inside the nozzle is grasped. And by making a laminated material, the impregnation state and mechanical characteristics of the three-dimensional molded product are grasped. The 3D printer used MF-2200 manufactured by MUTOH, which is a fused deposition modeling (FDM) method. The FDM method is a method of extruding while melting filamentary thermoplastic resin inside a nozzle heated by a heater, laminating one by one on the basis of data such as 3D CAD, and forming a three-dimensional object. In this research, CFRP was formed by independently producing and changing a nozzle suitable for forming CFRP using covering composite yarn. The laminated materials were alternately laminated in the 0 ° -90 ° direction, and the thickness of one layer was formed to be 0.25 mm. Pronterface was used for the control software of 3D printer, and G-CODE was created for each molding, read and molding was performed. In this study, the influence of the difference in molding conditions such as nozzle diameter and molding speed on the impregnation state and mechanical properties of the resin was investigated.

3. OUTLINE OF EXPERIMENT

3.1 SEM OBSERVATION

KEYENCE's VE-8800 was used as a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to observe the cross section of the sample. Before observation by SEM, the sample cross sections were polished in the order of 400, 1000, 2000, and a diamond buff. During observation, platinum was deposited on the observation cross section to prevent charge up of the sample. The ion sputtering apparatus used for film formation was JFC-1500 of JEOL Ltd., and the film thickness was 50 Å.

3.2 THREE-POINT BENDING TESTAFFILIATION

Three-point bending test was conducted to understand the bending strength of CFRP molded in this research. The testing machine used Shimadzu's AUTOGRAPH AG-I 100kN. The bending strength is calculated by the following equation.

$$\sigma_b = (3P_b L) / (2bh^2)$$

Here, σ_b [MPa] is the bending strength, P_b [N] is the maximum load, L [mm] is the distance between fulcrums, b [mm] the width of the test piece, and h [mm] the thickness of the test piece.

The sample preparation conditions were as follows: 10 layers were laminated at 0 ° -90 °, and a length of 100 mm and a width b of 10 mm were set and cut using a diamond cutter. The specimen thickness h [mm] was about 2.5 mm. The thickness of the test piece was measured three times each using a micrometer and a caliper, and the average value was used. The load-displacement relationship was continuously measured by a computer at a distance L between the fulcrums of 80 mm and a displacement speed of 5 mm / min, with the upper side of the CFRP as the contact side with the indenter. The number of tests under the same conditions was set to five.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 NOZZLE INTERNAL IMPREGNATION THEORY

It is considered that the resin infiltration inside the nozzle is melted by the resin covering the fiber bundle inside the heated nozzle, and proceeds by the pressure generated by the taper applied inside the nozzle. It is thought that the impregnating ability inside the nozzle is determined by the amount of fiber, resin amount and nozzle diameter in the covering composite yarn. If the cross-sectional area of

the portion where the nozzle diameter is the smallest is smaller than the sum of the fiber in the composite yarn and the resin cross-sectional area, the composite yarn cannot pass through the nozzle and fibers and resin accumulate inside the nozzle. Conversely, if the cross-sectional area of the nozzle diameter minimum is larger than the cross-sectional area of the composite yarn, pressure is not generated by the taper and impregnation does not proceed. When the nozzle diameter reaches a certain value, it becomes completely impregnated.

The percentage of resin impregnation in the fiber bundle is defined as the impregnation rate. Assuming that the diameter of CFRP in the case of 100% impregnation rate is φA , there are only resin and fibers in CFRP, so the cross-sectional area of the fiber is equal to the number of fibers of the cross-sectional area per fiber. The expression holds.

$$\varphi A = \sqrt{\frac{d_{cf}^2 \times N_{CF}}{V_f}}$$

Here, d_{cf} is the fiber diameter, N_{cf} is the number of fibers, and V_f is the fiber volume content.

Also, if the impregnation rate is not 100%, there are non-impregnated parts composed of air and fibers in the fiber bundle. Assuming that the fiber volume fraction in the non-impregnated part is equal to V_f and the diameter of the non-impregnated part when the proportion of the impregnated part is $X\%$ is φB , the cross-sectional area is the following. It is expressed by an expression.

$$\varphi B = \sqrt{(1-X) \times \varphi A^2}$$

Moreover, when the non-impregnated part exists, it is thought that the resin which was not impregnated remains around CFRP. Here, it is assumed that the amount of resin around CFRP is equal to the amount of air in the non-impregnated part. The cross-sectional area when the nozzle diameter in the presence of $(1-X)\%$ of the non-impregnated part is φC is equal to the sum of the cross-sectional area of CFRP and the resin cross-sectional area around CFRP when the impregnation rate is 100%. The expression holds.

$$\varphi C = \sqrt{(1-V_f)\varphi B^2 + \varphi A^2}$$

Assuming that no gap is formed between the extrusion part at the tip of the nozzle and CFRP, the CFRP diameter φC in the presence of the above-described non-impregnated part is equal to the nozzle diameter. Therefore, φC is defined as the theoretical nozzle diameter. In addition, the ratio of impregnation of resin in fiber bundle is defined as theoretical impregnation ratio, and the ratio of non-impregnated part in cross section is defined as porosity, and expressed using the following equation.

$$\text{Theoretical impregnation [\%]} = \frac{\left(\frac{\pi\varphi A^2}{4} - \frac{\pi\varphi B^2}{4}\right)}{\frac{\pi\varphi A^2}{4}} = \frac{\varphi A^2 - \varphi B^2}{\varphi A^2}$$

$$\text{Theoretical porosity [\%]} = \frac{\frac{\pi\varphi B^2}{4}}{\frac{\pi\varphi C^2}{4}} = \frac{\varphi B^2}{\varphi C^2}$$

In this study, we use 3K70d covering composite yarn. The nozzle diameter used in this experiment was a total of three nozzle diameters with an impregnation ratio of 82, 39, 0% and a nozzle diameter φ 0.64, 0.71, 0.80 mm. However, with a nozzle diameter of 0.61 mm, which has an impregnation rate of 99%, it was found that molding was difficult due to the lack of resin around fiber bundles from experimental results last year, so it was not used in molding of laminates.

At a molding speed of 20 mm / min, four nozzles with different diameters, φ 0.61, 0.64, 0.71, and 0.80 mm, were drawn vertically from the respective nozzles for molding, and cross-sectional observation was performed by SEM. By pulling it out vertically instead of pressing it on the table, it is possible to observe the impregnated state due to the influence of only the inside of the nozzle. The percentage of the unimpregnated part in the entire sample cross section was defined as the porosity in the experiment, and it was calculated from the SEM image. Fig.4.1 is the SEM image of each nozzle diameter. The relationship between the nozzle diameter and the theoretical porosity and the porosity calculated from the SEM image is shown in Fig. 4.2. The calculated porosity decreased as the nozzle diameter decreased, and showed a tendency close to the theoretical value. From this fact, it can be said that the resin impregnation inside the nozzle can be controlled by the nozzle diameter.

In addition, negative CFRP was observed when the laminate was formed and laminated under three conditions of nozzle diameter ϕ 0.64, 0.71, and 0.80 mm at a forming speed of 20 mm / min. The relationship between the nozzle diameter and the porosity of the drawn material and the porosity calculated from the SEM image is shown in Fig. 4.3. It is considered that the cause of the porosity of the laminated material being much lower than the porosity of the drawn material at any nozzle diameter is that pressure is applied to the CFRP by pressing the nozzle against the table and the impregnation of the resin progresses. When CFRP is formed by pressing the nozzle against the table, the impregnation of the resin greatly progresses by the pressure applied to the CFRP by pressing, and it can be said that the influence of the nozzle diameter on the resin impregnation property is small.

Fig.4.1: Cross section observation by SEM at each nozzle diameter

Fig.4.2: Porosity at each nozzle diameter

Fig.4.3: Relation between porosity and nozzle diameter of laminate and drawing material

4.2 INFLUENCE OF FORMING SPEED ON RESIN IMPREGNATION

At a nozzle diameter of 0.64 mm, the forming speed was divided into four stages of 20, 40, 100, and 400 mm / min, respectively, which were drawn vertically, respectively, and the cross section was observed by SEM. The SEM image of sample cross section is shown in Fig. 4.4. Therefore, the porosity became values close to the theoretical value when the forming speed was slow. However, it became higher than the theoretical value as the forming speed increased. It is considered that this is because the pressing time of the nozzle decreases as the forming speed increases and the resin is not impregnated into the CFRP.

Fig.4.4: Cross section observation of laminate by SEM at each nozzle diameter

4.2 BENDING TEST OF LAMINATED MATERIAL

The laminated material was formed under the three conditions of nozzle diameter ϕ 0.64, 0.71, and 0.80 mm at a forming speed of 20 mm / min and a clearance of 0.225 mm, and a bending test was performed. Fig.4.5 shows the SEM image of CFRP just after molding,

The stress deflection diagram for each nozzle diameter is shown in Fig. 4.6. The bending strength was in the order of nozzle diameter ϕ 0.64, ϕ 0.71, ϕ 0.80 mm. This is considered to be due to the fact that the smaller the nozzle diameter, the lower the proportion of voids that adversely affect the bending strength. An SEM image of the fracture surface of the laminated material is shown in Fig. 4.7. From this, it can be seen that the fractured surface is not vertical but curved at 0.80 mm, which has a high porosity.

Fig.4.5: Cross section observation of laminate by SEM at each nozzle diameter

Fig.4.6: Mean stress deflection diagram of laminate at each nozzle diameter

Fig.4.7: Bending fracture surface of laminate by SEM at each nozzle diameter

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we aimed to understand the influence of molding conditions when using CFRP with covering composite yarn in 3D printer on resin impregnation and mechanical properties. As a result, the following conclusions were obtained.

- (1) It was possible to control the impregnation state in the nozzle depending on the nozzle diameter.
- (2) When the nozzle diameter was small in the bending test, the bending strength increased.
- (3) In forming the laminate material, forming failure tends to occur when the nozzle diameter is small.

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